

HOT EXTRUSION OF Al_2O_3 WHISKER REINFORCED ALUMINUM MATRIX COMPOSITES AND THEIR MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

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ABSTRACT

To understand the effect of hot extrusion on MMC systematically, correlations between processing conditions and homogeneous dispersion of fibers are investigated for Al_2O_3 whisker reinforced Al composites. The primary product of MMC billet for hot extrusion is prepared by squeeze casting in two kinds of fiber volume fraction 10% and 20%. These different fiber volume fraction billets are extruded at different process conditions. The relation between the extrusion process parameters and the fiber debonding and the alignment are simulated by implicit finite debonding code (NIKE2D). Experimentally, the dispersion state of the fibers in the matrix is observed with respect to process parameters. The breakage of the fibers during hot extrusion is also observed. In order to compare the mechanical properties of extruded MMC with MMC billet, the tensile strength of hot extruded Al_2O_3 whisker reinforced Al matrix composites are measured from at room temperature up to 300 °C. By employing observed results systematically, correlation is proposed between the microstructural development of the fibers, mechanical properties, and the processing parameters.

KEYWORDS: Short fiber composites; Matrix, aluminum; Hot extrusion; Micromechanics.

1. INTRODUCTION

Wide application of metal matrix composite (MMC)s for high performance engineering fields have been disturbed by the high production cost of MMCs caused by unstable manufacturing processes and expensive reinforcement fibers. The forming of MMCs therefore has been considered to solve these hinderances with cheap discontinuous ceramic fibers such as alumina short fiber reinforced MMC billets [1-2]. In general, discontinuous fibers in MMC billets are randomly oriented so that the mechanical properties of these

discontinuous fiber reinforced MMCs are lower than the half of those of continuous fiber reinforced MMCs according to the simple relation by the rule of mixture[3]. Therefore, the secondary forming of MMCs is expected to align discontinuous fibers to the applied load direction during its process. Extrusion at elevated temperatures has received a considerable amount of attention among several secondary forming of MMCs such as rolling and forging[4-6] because of its excellent preferential axial alignment of discontinuous fibers. However, this secondary forming process have addressed the optimization of the process so as to avoid fiber fracture, debonding and other microstructural damage relative to its advantage of fiber alignment. There have been several attempts to build optimum processing range of temperature, strain rate and plastic strain field for minimization of fiber damage and maximization of fiber alignment during fabrication[7-9]. However, there are a number of unclear points remain due to the lack of fundamental mechanisms by which the deformation of heterogeneous materials and the progressive fiber fracture take place. This study is therefore tried to describe the systematic correlations between processing conditions and subsequent results such as fiber alignment, fiber damages, and mechanical properties in hot extrusion. In order to complement such goals, theoretical analysis is performed by the adoption of the finite element method which is now widely used to simulate the metal forming process. A micro cell is introduced for the study of the microscopic behavior of MMC. The process conditions for hot extrusion of 20% reduction are examined with respect to fiber alignment and die angles. Experimental approach is also performed by hot extrusion tests of short fiber reinforced $Al_2O_3/Al-12\%Si$ (AA339) which supplied by Nippon Light Metal Co. Ltd.. The fiber distribution and the fiber breakage of as received and hot extruded $Al_2O_3/Al-12\%Si$ MMCs are observed with respect to the extrusion die angle and velocity. The change of interface morphology is also investigated by using scanning electron microscopy(SEM). Tensile strengths are measured at different temperatures to know the effects of the hot extrusion on mechanical properties of MMCs.

2. THEORETICAL APPROACH

In this study, NIKE2D is chosen to simulate the MMC hot extrusion. NIKE2D is a implicit finite deformation code for analyzing the static and dynamic response of 2-D solids[10]. The code has been proven good to deal with contact conditions. Such capability is essential to properly simulate the interface debonding and sliding between the fiber and the matrix. The friction coefficient and the debonding criterion are set to be .1 and .3 of plastic strain along the interface. It is speculated that the debonding might occur due to the maximum principal stress and, thus, the debonding criterion of plastic strain might not be appropriate. At the present moment, however, it is the only available criterion in the code. Its value is determined by comparing the results of numerical simulations and experiments several times. The present study is carried out with regard to the die angle and the fiber

alignment for investigating their effects to the microscopic mechanism. Figure 1 shows the MMC extrusion model. The reduction ratio, friction coefficient, and the fiber volume fraction are set to be 20%, 0, and 10%, respectively. The load condition is given with the prescribed displacements at the one end of the billet. An unit cell is located at the center of the billet. Its size is one hundredth of other finite elements so that the size effect of the cell can be minimized. Four cases of extrusion process are simulated regarding the die angle and the fiber alignment; (1) case1 : $\alpha = \tan^{-1}(1/2)$, $\beta = 45^\circ$, (2) case2 : $\alpha = \tan^{-1}(1/2)$, $\beta = -45^\circ$, (3) case3 : $\alpha = \tan^{-1}(1/3)$, $\beta = 45^\circ$, (4) case4 : $\alpha = \tan^{-1}(1/3)$, $\beta = -45^\circ$. The simulations are performed under the assumption that the interface is either perfectly bonded or breakable as well.

Figure 1. A MMC extrusion model

3. EXPERIMENTAL APPROACH

3.1 MMC Billets Billets of short fiber Al_2O_3 reinforced Al-12%Si matrix MMCs are used as raw materials for hot extrusion. These billets are fabricated by squeeze casting and supplied by Nippon Light Metal Co. Ltd.. The volume fractions of reinforcement in these billets are two kinds of 10 vol. % and 20 vol. %. As-squeeze cast microstructures are illustrated in Figure 2 (a) for 10 vol. % and (b) for 20 vol. % MMC. Figure 2 (a) exhibits a homogeneous fiber distribution in an approximately random array with irregular fiber length. However, Figure 2 (b) shows somewhat inhomogeneous and preferential fiber direction normal to the paper plane even though its fiber volume fraction is higher than Figure 2 (a).

(a)

(b)

Figure 2. Microstructures of squeeze cast $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Al-12\%Si}$ MMC

(a) 10 % fiber volume fraction (b) 20 % fiber volume fraction

3.2 Hot Extrusion of MMCs Squeeze cast $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Al-12\%Si}$ MMC billets of 35 mm diameter are extruded under various conditions with using the 25 ton press and the experimental set-up as shown in Figure 3. Conical dies are employed as shown in Figure 4 and the dimensions for different dies and their extrusion ratios are summarized in Table 1.

Figure 3. Experimental set-up for hot extrusion

Figure 4. Dies for hot extrusion

Die No	α angle	D1	D2	L	h	H	Extrusion Ratio : R
1	20	35	26.1	15	4	25	1.8
2	30	35	20.2	15	4	25	3.0

Table 1. Dimensions of dies and extrusion ratios

The extrusion temperature is fixed at 400 °C and controlled within + 3 °C fluctuation. The extrusion speeds of 0.5 mm/min and 2 mm/min are employed from the previous experimental results for defect free surface. The die surfaces are coated with the lubricant of 1:1 mixture of grease oil and graphite powder.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Theoretical Observation Figure 4 shows the hot extruded billet of MMC when the micro cell is out from the die exit. Figure 5 demonstrates the detail deformations near the fiber inside of the micro-cell with the die angle of $\alpha = \tan^{-1} (1/2)$; (a) $\beta = 45^\circ$ and (b) $\beta = -45^\circ$. Similarly, Figure 6 does the case of $\alpha = \tan^{-1} (1/3)$; (a) $\beta = 45^\circ$ and (b) $\beta = -45^\circ$. As seen in the figures, the angle of the fiber alignment is reduced after the hot extrusion in all cases; from 45° to 25° . The positive angle of fiber alignment with steeper die angle (here, case 1) could induce severe damage along the interface bonding. As expected, the lower die angle improves such debonding failure. Figure 7 shows the distribution of the maximum principal stress inside of the fiber with the perfectly bonded interface of case (1). In this case the maximum value reaches 2.4GPa, much higher than fiber strength, and thus the fiber fracture could occur. This could explain that higher bonding strength is not always recommended.

Figure 5. The extruded shape of the billet

(a) $\beta = 45^\circ$

(b) $\beta = -45^\circ$

Figure 6. The detail deformations in the micro-cell with the die angle of $\alpha = \tan^{-1}(1/2)$

(a) $\beta = 45^\circ$

(b) $\beta = -45^\circ$

Figure 7. The detail deformations in the micro-cell with the die angle of $\alpha = \tan^{-1}(1/3)$

Figure 8. The distribution of the max. principal stress in the perfectly bonded fiber of case (1)

4.2 Extrusion Load and Ram Displacement Figure 9 shows the relation between the extrusion load and the ram displacement for 20 vol. % $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Al}$ -12%Si MMC when the die angle 2α is 30° and the extrusion speed is 0.5 mm/min with 400°C extrusion temperature. Compared with the relation for 7075 Al alloy shown in Figure 9, the extrusion load for MMCs is obviously more required and complicated. Dislocations in the matrix containing obstacles such as the fibers here may be relevant to explain this result with the work-hardening rate and the flow stress of the matrix[1]. Figure 10 shows different behaviors between 20° die angle and 30° die angle for 10 vol. % $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Al}$ -12%Si MMC under the extrusion speed 2 mm/min and 400°C extrusion temperature. It is naturally expected that the larger die angle requires more extrusion load. From Figures 9 and 10, it is shown that 10 vol. % MMC with 4 times higher extrusion speed than 20 vol. % MMC is required more extrusion force than 20 vol. % MMC. Thus, the fiber volume fraction and the extrusion speed is interconnected with the extrusion force in the same way.

Figure 9. The relation between the extrusion load and the ram displacement with 20 vol. % MMC

Figure 10. The relation between the extrusion load and the ram displacement with 10 vol. % MMC

4. 3 Microstructural Observations The microstructural change by hot extrusion is illustrated with as-squeeze cast MMC micrograph in Figure 11. It is shown that the fiber distribution of 20 vol. % $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Al}-12\%\text{Si}$ is aligned to the extrusion direction as well as more segregation of Si in the matrix alloy. It is supposed that the extrusion temperature 400 °C helps to cause the segregation of Si by the diffusion during the heating of the matrix alloy. All the micrographs are taken normal to the extrusion direction and the hot extrusion condition is that the extrusion speed is 0.5 mm/min and the die angle is 40 °. The extrusion temperature is fixed at 400 °C for all the cases in this study. Figure 12 shows the effect of the die angle on the fiber distribution for 10 vol. % MMC under 2 mm/min extrusion speed. The die angle of 20 ° influences less than the die angle of 30 ° for the fiber alignment. Relative Figure 10, it can be explained that less die angle requires less extrusive force which makes less effective for the fiber alignment.

(a) (b)
Figure 11. Fiber distribution of
20 vol. % $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Al}-12\%\text{Si}$
(a) as-squeeze cast (b) hot extruded

(a) (b)
Figure 12. The effect of die angle
for the fiber distribution
(a) die angle 20 ° (b) die angle 30 °

The effects of the extrusion speed and the fiber volume fraction are also illustrated in Figure 13. The fiber alignment with 2 mm/min extrusion speed is shown more effective than with 0.5 mm/min extrusion speed. It is understood by the comparison between the extrusion force and the extrusion speed in Figure 9 and 10. The extrusion force is increased with the increasing extrusion speed. However, the higher extrusion force by the extrusion speed causes disadvantageous effect for the fiber breakage as shown in Figure 14. The fiber breakage is happened with 2mm/min extrusion speed. It is also shown from Figure 13 (b) and (c) that higher fiber volume fraction MMC billet is more conglomerated for the fibers under the extrusion condition - 0.5 mm/min extrusion speed with 30 ° die angle.

Figure 13. The effect of the extrusion speed and the volume fraction of MMC billet
 (a) extrusion speed 2 mm/min, 10 vol. % (b) extrusion speed 0.5 mm/min, 10 vol. %
 (c) extrusion speed 0.5 mm/min, 20 vol. %

Figure 14. SEM micrograph of the fiber/matrix interface
 (a) 2mm/min extrusion speed (b) 0.5 mm/min extrusion speed

4.4 Strength of Hot Extruded MMC The tensile strength of hot extruded MMC billets are measured at different temperature to investigate the effect of hot extrusion on the mechanical properties of MMCs. The values of hot extruded MMCs are compared with those of as-squeeze cast MMCs at different temperatures in Figure 15. In general, it is

found that the tensile strengths of hot extruded MMCs are increased more than about 25 % compared with those of same fiber volume fraction as-squeeze cast MMCs at room temperature. However, the strengths are even decreased little bit at high temperature 300 °C. It is obviously expected that the effect of the hot extrusion enhances the fiber conglomeration and the fiber alignment even though which one contributes more for the strength is unknown.

Figure 15. Tensile strengths of hot extruded MMCs

In several processing parameters, the effect of the die angle on the fiber conglomeration and subsequent increment of the fiber volume fraction and the mechanical properties is investigated for 20 ° to 40 ° die angle. The tensile strength of hot extruded 10 vol. % MMC billets with 30 ° die angle shows higher value than that with 20 ° die angle. However, with 20 vol. % MMC billets between 30 ° and 40 ° die angle, it results in opposite phenomena. Therefore, 30 ° may be critical die angle in a limited extrusion condition. The extrusion speed is also concerned with the tensile strength for 10 vol. % MMC billets. The extrusion speed of 0.5 mm/min gives higher tensile strength than 2 mm/min. It is understood that the extrusion speed is involved with the fiber/matrix bonding as well as the fiber alignment. The fractographical observation of hot extruded specimens with different die angles

supports this idea as shown in Figure 16. A number of fiber debonding with incomplete alignment are found in MMC hot extruded with high extrusion speed.

Figure 16. Fractograph of hot extruded MMC (a) 2mm/min extrusion speed
(b) 0.5 mm/min extrusion speed

6. CONCLUSION

1. With the introduction of a micro-cell, the microscopic mechanism of the fiber and the matrix is studied regarding process parameters such as the die angle and the fiber alignment during MMC hot extrusion. Although such study can provide the qualitative results, the process failure such as the interface debonding or the fiber breakage could be explained so that the results can be helpful to the process design; negative fiber angle or less steep die angle could give better products.
2. The fiber distribution and the fiber/matrix interface morphology as well as the tensile strength are related to the processing parameters of hot extrusion in parallel. Within limited range (less than 30° die angle), higher die angle and extrusion speed is more effective to obtain higher mechanical properties even though the fiber breakage is more happened.
3. The results of the microscopic finite deformation analysis and the experiments show similar tendency qualitatively in limited process range. There are further study required particularly the debonding mechanism to complete the general process range.

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7. REFERENCES

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